

Research Article

Postgraduate Studies in Nigerian Universities: Issues and Implications

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Abstract

This study is on Postgraduate Studies in Nigerian Universities: Issues and implications. The study employed a descriptive survey method and questionnaire was the instrument used for data collection. The total population for this study is 1,247 students. The sample size for the study was put at 30% (374) and was considered adequate using systematic sampling technique. The data obtained from the copies of questionnaires retrieved from respondents were analyzed using frequency count and percentages to answer the research questions. It was revealed from the study that Poor supervision as a result of under-qualified and inexperience supervisors, lack of sound research knowledge on the part of students, and poor relationship between supervisors and students among others are the major problems postgraduate students in Edo and Delta states encountered during the course of their programme. The study revealed that delay in the completion of the programmes, abandonment/high dropout rate and falling standard of Postgraduate Programme/Education are some of the major implications of Postgraduate Programme in Universities in Edo and Delta states. The study recommends that there is need for well-structured relationship between supervisors and their students to enhance smooth and commendable study. The act of rebuking and warding off or scaring away or shouting at mature students is not the answer to seriousness in learning.

Key words: Postgraduate studies, Universities, Edo, Delta, Nigeria, Problems, Implications.

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Introduction

Wikipedia (2009) posits that postgraduate education involves studying for degrees or other qualification for which a First or Bachelor's Degree is required and is normally considered to be part of Tertiary or Higher Education. This level is generally referred to as graduate school in North America. Although, systems of Higher Education go back to Ancient Greek, China, India and Africa, the concept of Postgraduate education depends upon the system of awarding degree at different levels(Wikipedia, 2009). According to Wikipedia, there are basically two main types of qualification studied for at the postgraduate level, which are academics and vocational degrees. The study habit of postgraduate students' is a contributing factor to either the smooth running of the programme or increase in the prospects of a possible dropout from the programme. Nneji (2002) posits that reading is an attempt to absorb the thought of the author and know what the author is conveying. Study habits are very crucial for postgraduate students. Nneji states that study habits are learning tendencies that enable student work privately. Fielden (2004) states that good study habits help the students in skill acquisition/outcomes such as in selecting, analyzing, critiquing and synthesizing. Efficient study habit is a step towards the success of the programme. The concepts of the study habits of postgraduate students have been taken for granted among postgraduate students in developing countries and thereby contribute immensely to the decline in the running of the programme. Igun and Adogbeji (2007) opine that solving these problems and giving proper orientation to all Nigerian postgraduate students on study habits would ensure that they move closer to completing the programme at the normal duration.

Statement of the Problem

Postgraduate education involves studying for higher degrees or other qualifications after completing a first or Bachelor's Degree. This level is generally referred to as graduate school in North America. Postgraduate education depends upon the system of awarding higher degree at different levels such as Postgraduate Diploma, Masters and Doctor of Philosophy. Research is hallmark of postgraduate programmes. Majority of the students that enrolled into the programme are adults and working class who needs the degree to advance in their chosen profession and as such, desire to complete the programme in a record time. However, the case seems different attracting several criticisms. There are claims that the system is bedeviled with all sorts of problems. Hence, it is commonly alleged in Nigeria today that if one wishes to undergo postgraduate studies without tears, one should get out of the country to do so. Some people have even sworn not to study at the postgraduate level in Nigeria. It is against

this background that, this study is therefore set out to identify or analyze the problems of Postgraduate Studies in Nigerian Universities: Issues and implications in Selected Universities in Edo and Delta States of Nigeria.

Research Questions

- What are the factors inhibiting postgraduate studies in universities in Edo and Delta states?
- What are the implications of the problems encountered by postgraduate students?

Literature Review

There are a lot of problems that engulf postgraduate programmes in Nigerian Universities. Igun and Adogbeji (2007) posited that dwindling funding affects the development of postgraduate schools in Nigeria. External overseas assistance and scholarships are hard to acquire. Poor national economy is also a contributing factor. The lack of funding has created a problem of retaining experience and qualifies instructors who find better job elsewhere. The scholars further stressed that frequent strike actions and closure of university causes delays postgraduate programme as student is delayed from graduating on time as a result of this problem. Students are force to pay accumulated school fees resulting from the delay cause by the strike action they know nothing about. Postgraduate studies in Edo and Delta States are faced with some institutional based problems of different kinds such as research, teaching and cost. Koen (2007) opines that students' success is dependent on the quality of institutional organisation, the extent of organisational resources and the quality of academics and institutional provisioning. Koen observed in his study of Masters' students' retention and success that recent expansion of Master enrolment and of Master's programme has contributed to institutional dislocation. The author further stressed that the departments continue to lack a supporting university framework and are considerably short of resources along with this, the approaches of academics in departments also differ enormously. The author posits that the increase in enrolment and graduation of postgraduate students to a great extent depend on the existing pool of PhDs to provide adequate supervision support to the growing number of PGDE, MA and PhD Students.

Koen listed the following responses as some of the problems of postgraduate studies:

- a.) Some supervisors do not have enough experience
- b.) Long bureaucratic procedures concerning the approval of research proposal
Language problems

- c.) Lack of committee and motivation of students
- d.) Ineffective procedure concerning the approval of research proposals.

In developing countries like Nigeria, some supervisors showed little interest in students' progress and often rebuke and disrespect them whenever they come seeking for assistance. Institutions, society and government are often blamed for the problems confronting postgraduate student, rebuffing the fact that students also incur some problems for themselves. In this part of the world, when you are through with your First Degree Programme, you automatically become an independent or many people are looking forward to you irrespective of the high rate of unemployment in the country; which has an adverse effect on students' who want to make a step further in their education. Many writers have alluded to low and inadequate state supported funding, the disadvantaged status of students and their need for financial support (Koen, 2007). Elphinestone(2002) avers that at some stages, the rational, happy students you started supervising become anxious and angry. It must be noted that the research work is almost certainly the biggest and most important piece of academic work the student has ever undertake and may ever undertake. Elphinestoneenumerated the following as the problem facing postgraduate students especially in the area of supervisors and research:

- a.) Avoidance of the supervisor which will eventually have negative implication on the smooth completion of the programme.
- b.) Unwillingness to commit ideas and literature review material on paper.
- c.) Unwillingness to be committed to a research topic and continually changing direction after initial period of exploration. The scholar however asserted that some academics show little interest in students and abandon some, other academics are hard taskmasters. The implication of this is that when Masters' students make the transition from knowledge consumer (course work students) to knowledge producers (Thesis or dissertation writers) they face either continued dislocation or some form integration. It may interest you know that scholarships for postgraduate programme from states and federal government funded programme have reduced drastically in Nigeria. This is very visible in universities in Edo and Delta States. Problems of supervision cannot be rebut here, and those of Poor relationship between supervisors and students as well as problems with research design and writing extended academic texts are reasons for non-retention, dropout and delay in completing the programme. Students experience difficulty in conceptualizing studies and struggle to write Thesis or Dissertation. Koen

opines that neglect of research training due to the fact that research training is time consuming and fraught with learning errors and time delays as another crucial students based problems.

The role of the Society in the problems encountered by postgraduate students shall be x-rayed in this section. According to Holderness (2000), in terms of apartheid under education, the dominant focus of the literature on Master's students is aimed at the learning problems of students. It is clear that students are rushed through a theory based kind of training, self-superficial and then are completely incapable of doing the very basic research manipulations required for advanced study (Koen, 2007). Koen remain stunned by students who cannot do basic statistics at Master's and doctoral levels, who cannot talk intelligently about research instrument at any level of sophistication. Postgraduate students are faced with a lot of problems that have direct or indirect implication to the completion of their studies. On issue of finance, Dezoysa(1999) posits that most postgraduate students do not possess a sound economic background. This situation may have had influence on their research and smooth running of the programme. Dezoysa further stressed that, despite their limited income only a few have received financial aid from their institution in form of research grants or their state in form of bursary or scholarship. Hommedia (1999) revealed in his study that inadequate allocation of funds for research work in the third world countries has become an obvious obstacle to postgraduate students. Some postgraduate students combine studies with their career. Dezoysa (1999) carried out a study and revealed that some postgraduate students are not granted study leave by their respective organizations. This factor may have affected the successful completion of research work. Research students may have faced difficulties in conducting research work while holding career responsibility. Inadequate allocation of time and lack of time management may have made a significant contribution towards postgraduate students' failure (Wanasinghe, 1999).

Inability to devote sufficient time is one of the major reasons cited by the drop out of the respondents for not completing their studies (Dezoysa, 1999). Inadequate writing is a direct result of inadequate reading and studying (Simmons, 2002). Postgraduate students are scholars in training and have the responsibility of becoming prolific and critical writers in their disciplines and careers. In Africa, there is widespread reading in all scholarly fields, but less is being achieved in writing and publication (Igun and Adogbeji, 2007). Igun and Adogbeji went further opined that efficient study habits can strengthen writing and that professors in the developing countries such as those in Nigeria Universities should attempt to equip graduates with high level of analytical

skills, capacity for critical reasoning, self-reflection and conceptual grasp and ability to learn autonomously and exercise flexibility of mind (Simmons, 2002). Liu (2005) posits that study habit is actually improving because of the advent and wide use of the internet, hypertext and multimedia resource. Inadequate basic facilities such as conducive lecture halls, library facilities and internet facilities affect postgraduate studies. Library facilities produced for students seem as adequate for some students and inadequate for others which have negative implications on those whose needs are not met (Ismail, 1997). Rotimi (2007) described most of our Universities as “Glorified Nursery schools” due to the numerous and unaddressed problems militating against smooth learning and completion of postgraduate programmes in our Universities.

Some supervisors are inexperienced and have insufficient knowledge of the relevant field, change of supervisors as a result of the transfer of the previous supervisor to another institution, supervisor’s other work load, allowing students to proceed with research work without proper guidance in research methodology and lack of support by supervisors had led to delay in completing research programme or a total dropout (Dezoysa, 1999). Duze (1997) opines that in spite of the availability or provision of the postgraduate programme in our universities, many Nigerians prefer to study abroad. Attitude of some lecturers or supervisors towards postgraduate students in this part of the world is nothing to write home about. Bad educational policies and inability to implement the existing policies accordingly either on the part of the government or the institution also affect postgraduate students. Hommedia(1999) had conducted research studies on Higher Education in the third world countries to reveal constraints which affect the completion of postgraduate studies. The scholar revealed that the absence of an adequate policy and programming of research work in the Universities, reluctance to allocate funds for research, inadequate resource, the failure to allocate staff time for research, the lack of commitment and inadequate or incompetence of supervisors are the major impediments to both research and completion of the programme and thereby constitute a number of negative implication on postgraduate studies. For example, in Nigeria a masters’ degree programme is design for eighteen academic calendar months (a year and six months) but today, students spend three or more years before they can complete the programme.

Methodology

This study employed a descriptive design to examine the problem of postgraduate studies in some selected universities in Edo and Delta states. The population of this study consisted of students undertaking postgraduate degree programmes in Education

(Ph.D, M.Ed and PGDE) in three universities in Edo and Delta states. The Universities therefore are: University of Benin (Uniben), Ambrose All University, Ekpoma; and Delta State University, Abraka. They are 1,247 students. The sample size for the study was put at 30% (374) and was considered adequate using systematic sampling technique of the respective universal population of the study. The questionnaire entitled "Analysis of Problems of Postgraduate Studies' of Some Selected Universities in Edo and Delta States Questionnaire (APPSSUQ)" was chosen as the instrument for data collection. The questionnaire is made up of two parts (A and B). The first part (A) consists of Biographical (Demographic) data such as name of institution, programme of study etc. The second part (B) is made up of structures statements or items aimed at eliciting information or data on the problems of postgraduate students. The data obtained from the copies of questionnaires retrieved from respondents were analyzed using frequency count and percentages.

Results and Discussions

Table1 Respondents' Programme of Study

Programme	Number of Respondents	Percentage	Rank
PGDE	148	41%	2
M.Ed	186	52%	1
Ph.D	26	7%	3
Total	360	100%	-

Table 1 shows the respondents programme of study. Master's in education (M.Ed) 186 (52%) ranked highest or first. Followed by Postgraduate Diploma in Education (PGDE) with 48 (41%) and Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D) came last with 26 (7%). This is an indication that more students enrolled into M.Ed Programme than other levels of postgraduate programmes in the universities in Edo and Delta states.

Research Question One (I)

What are the major factors (problems) militating against postgraduate studies in Universities in Edo and Delta State?

Table 2: Factors Militating against Postgraduate Studies in Universities in Edo and Delta states.

PROBLEMS	SA	A	No	%	RANK	D	SD	No	%	GRAND TOTAL	
										No	%
Lack of sound research knowledge by student	199	89	288	80	2	45	27	72	11	360	100
Inconsistency in the duration of the programme	191	66	257	71	7	55	48	103	29	360	100
Poor supervision as a result of under-qualified and inexperienced supervisors	231	65	296	82	1	42	22	64	18	360	100
Inadequate staff strength	194	56	250	69	8	84	26	110	31	360	100
Poor and inadequate facilities	201	62	263	73	6	24	73	97	27	360	100
Financial problems	197	73	270	75	4	48	42	90	25	360	100
Unnecessary insult/embarrassment of postgraduate students by lecturers or supervisors	199	96	295	82	1	44	21	65	18	360	100

Combination of job with study effects	166	77	243	68	9	97	20	117	32	360	100
Poor relationship between supervisors and student	211	70	281	78	3	63	16	79	22	360	100
Academic laziness on the part of students	103	29	132	37	12	112	116	228	63	360	100
Strike effects on P.G programme	155	91	246	68	9	69	45	114	32	360	100
Poor study habit on the part of the student	57	122	179	50	11	88	93	181	50	360	100
Poor government and institutional policies	88	177	265	74	5	67	28	95	26	360	100

SA(strongly Agree) ,A(Agree) ,D(Disagree), SD(Strongly Disagree).

Table2 shows the problems militating against postgraduate studies in Edo and Delta states universities. A majority of the respondents responded to poor supervision as a result of under qualified and inexperienced supervisors and unnecessary insult/embarrassment of postgraduate students by lecturers or supervisors ranked first (1) with 296(82%) and 295(82%) respectively. Lack of sound research knowledge by the students ranked second (2) with 288 (80%). Also, poor relationship between supervisors and students came third (3) with 281 (78%). Others are financial problems with 270 (75%), Poor government and institutional policies 265(74%), Poor and inadequate facilities with 263(73%), Inconsistency in the duration of the programme with 257(71%) and Inadequate staff strength with 250(69%). However, it may interest you to know that all the problems enlisted in the study received positive response. This is a further indication that postgraduate students in Edo and Delta states Universities experienced these problems in the course of their studies which may lead to negative implications. These problems had succeeded in reducing our universities to “gloried secondary schools”. This Finding support the work of Rotimi (2007) who described most of our Universities as “Glorified Nursery schools” due to the numerous and unaddressed problems militating against smooth learning and completion of postgraduate programmes in our Universities. These findings is also in congruence with the study of

Koen (2007) who posits that some supervisors showed little interest in students' progress and often rebuke them whenever they come seeking for assistance.

Research Question Two (2)

What are the implications of the problems encountered by Postgraduate Students on their studies?

Table 3 Implication of the problems by postgraduate students on their studies

Implication			Sub-Total					Sub-Total			GRAND TOTAL	
	SA	A	No	%	RANK	D	SD	No	%	RANK	No	%
Abandonment and high dropout rate of the programme	198	72	270	75	2	33	57	90	25	7	360	100
Delay in the completion of the programme	204	81	275	76	1	59	26	85	24	8	360	100
Frustration	99	48	147	41	8	39	174	213	59	1	360	100
Poor academic performance	101	61	162	45	7	111	87	198	55	2	360	100
Poor quality of project/desertion/thesis writing/preparation	133	53	186	52	5	52	122	174	48	4	360	100
Low turnout of senior academic (Ph.D holders)	176	83	259	72	4	41	60	101	28	5	360	100
Falling standard of P.G. Programme/ Education	99	163	262	73	3	73	25	98	27	6	360	100

SA(strongly Agree) ,A(Agree) ,D(Disagree), SD(Strongly Disagree).

Table 3 shows the implication of the problems postgraduate student on their programme. Thus: delay in the completion of the programme ranked (1) with 275 (76%). Abandonment and high dropout rate of the programme followed closely with 275 (75%); while falling standard of Postgraduate programme/Education ranked third (3) with 262 (73%). Low turnout of senior academic (Ph.D holders) ranked (4) with 259 (72%). Poor quality of project/desertion/thesis writing/ preparation ranked (5) with 186(52%). This study simply reveals that delay in the completion of the programme, abandonment and high dropout rate of the programme, falling standard of Postgraduate programme/Education, Low turnout of senior academics (Ph.D holders) and Poor quality of project/desertion/thesis writing/ preparation are the resultant effect of the problems discuss in table3 above. The findings corroborate the study of De Zoysa (1999) who posited that some supervisors, are inexperience and have insufficient knowledge of the relevant fields incessant changes supervisors due to transfer to other institution and other reasons such as high supervision's workload, allowing students to process their research work without proper guidance, molestation of students and lack of support by the supervisors had also led to delay in completing postgraduate programmes or total dropout. This finding complements the study of Duze (1997) who opines that in spite of the availability or provision of the postgraduate programme in our universities, many Nigerians including those in Edo and Delta states prefer to study abroad.

Findings of the Study

- Poor supervision as a result of under-qualified and inexperience supervisors, unnecessary insult/embarrassment of postgraduate students by lecturers or supervisors, Lack of sound research knowledge by the students, poor relationship between supervisors and students, Poor government and institutional policies, Poor and inadequate facilities, Inconsistency in the duration of the programme and Inadequate staff strength are the major problems postgraduate students in Edo and Delta states encountered during the course of their programme.
- The study revealed that delay in the completion of the programmes, abandonment/high dropout rate and falling standard of Postgraduate Programme/Education are some of the major implications of Postgraduate Programmes in Universities in Edo and Delta states.

Conclusion

The study indicated that postgraduate studies in Edo-Delta states universities are bedeviled by several problems. In other words, postgraduate programmes in Edo and Delta states universities are plagued with a lot of problems such as Poor supervision as a result of under-qualified and inexperienced supervisors, lack of sound research knowledge on the part of students, poor relationship between supervisors and students that results to prolonged study duration, abandonment/high dropout rate and falling standard of Postgraduate Programme/Education by the students. Postgraduate programmes therefore appear discouraging and disheartening. No wonder, most intending postgraduate students prefer to study abroad.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are hereby made:

- I. University authorities should ensure that capable, qualified and experienced supervisors are engaged to supervise postgraduate students.
- II. Universities administration and other relevant bodies should organize training for inexperienced and newly employed academic staff especially in the area of research and supervision, knowing full well that research is the hallmark of postgraduate education.
- III. There is need for well-structured relationship between supervisors and their students to enhance smooth and commendable study. The act of rebuking and warding off or scaring away or shouting at mature students is not the answer to seriousness in learning.

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